

Adaptation of the Enterprise's HR-management in the Conditions of Threats

Valeriia Peniuk 1*

¹ Chernivtsi Institute of Trade and Economics of State University of Trade and Economics, Chernivtsi (Ukraine). PhD in Economics, Senior Lecturer.

* *Corresponding author*, e-mail: penyuk1992@gmail.com.

ARTICLE INFO

Received:

21 March 2024

Revised:

25 March 2024

Accepted:

27 March 2024

Published online:

4 April 2024

Copyright © 2024
by author

DOI: [10.5281/
zenodo.11063766](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11063766)

**Citation in APA
style**

ABSTRACT

HR teams of various enterprises around the world (including Ukrainian enterprises) first faced the pandemic, and today, Russian aggression, and were forced to quickly adapt the rules and directions of personnel management in the languages of these threats. We have proposed the following to the basic rules of personnel management: show more participation and empathy towards colleagues, create instructions on actions in the event of any critical situations, review employee productivity bars, check strategies for interaction in the team and work with personnel. We have formed 5 basic directions of joint work of HR teams and business in crisis periods, among them: assessment of the impact of threats on personnel management, relocation of employees, protection of employees, organization of work and ensuring the continuity of business processes.

Key words

adaptation, HR manager, HR team, threats.

Peniuk, V. (2024). Adaptation of the enterprise's HR-management in the conditions of threats. *2024 1st International Conference Contemporary Challenges of Socio-Economic Development for Public Policy, Legal Practice and Business Administration* (No. 13man3), Warsaw, Poland. East European Association of Scientists. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11063766>

Адаптація HR-менеджменту підприємства в умовах загроз

Валерія Олександрівна Пенюк 1*

¹ Чернівецький торговельно-економічний інститут Державного торговельно-економічного університету, Чернівці (Україна). Кандидат економічних наук, старший викладач.

* *Автор-кореспондент*, e-mail: penyuk1992@gmail.com.

СТАТТЯ

отримана:

20 березня 2024 р.

переглянута:

24 березня 2024 р.

прийнята:

25 березня 2024 р.

опублікована

онлайн:

4 квітня 2024 р.

Авторське право

© 2024 автора

DOI: [10.5281/](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11063766)

[zenodo.11063766](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11063766)

Цитування:

АНОТАЦІЯ

HR-команди різних підприємств світу (в т.ч. підприємств України) спочатку зіткнулись з пандемією, а сьогодні з російською агресією та вимушені швидко адаптувати правила та напрями управління персоналом в мовах цих загроз. До основних правил управління персоналом нами запропоновано наступні: проявляти більше участі та емпатії до колег, створити інструктажі щодо дій при настанні будь-яких критичних ситуацій, переглянути планки продуктивності працівників, перевірити стратегії взаємодії в колективі та роботі з персоналом. Нами сформовано 5 базових напрямів спільної роботи HR-команд і бізнесу по роботі в кризових періодах, серед них: оцінка впливу загроз на управління персоналом, переміщення працівників, захист працівників, організація роботи та забезпечення постійності бізнес-процесів.

Ключові слова

адаптація, HR-менеджер, HR-команда, загрози.

Peniuk V. O. Adaptation of the enterprise's HR-management in the conditions of threats. *Contemporary Challenges of Socio-Economic Development for Public Policy, Legal Practice and Business Administration* : 1st International Conference, March 28-29, 2024. Warsaw, Poland : East European Association of Scientists, 2024. No. 13man3. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11063766>

Introduction / Вступ

The post-pandemic period and the difficult conditions of the war in which Ukraine is today can become the driver of important changes in the process of managing enterprises and its components (including personnel management). If at the beginning of the war it was important to focus on the safety and health of your employees, today, due to the uncertainty of the duration of the war, it is important to ensure their stability. If earlier a large number of people were focused on development and career growth, now it has become more important to have adaptation to work in such conditions and financial stability to provide for oneself and one's family.

Results / Результати

In dangerous working conditions, the HR manager must show himself with maximum empathy, be able to put himself in the place of the employee, look at the situation from her point of view, let's say play the role of a psychologist, friend, facilitator, that is, a person who will help cope with everyday threats or problems, and also to help adapt to today's realities. That is why the main goal of the study is to determine the main rules/directions of personnel management in threat languages.

Adaptation of the team to the current circumstances is the primary task for every HR manager in Ukraine at the moment. The basic rules of adaptation include the following rules (Peniuk, 2020, p. 146):

1. Show more participation and empathy towards colleagues, because humanity is paramount. Sometimes just listening to a person can help you ten times better than trying any other methods of interaction

2. Creation of briefings on actions in the event of any critical situations and air alarms (missile threats). People should have a clear algorithm of what to do. This increases the feeling of security and reduces stress.

3. View performance charts and KPIs (personal tasks and plans). Stress affects everyone. Someone can more or less cope with it independently and work productively, but most people have reduced work efficiency. This should be taken into account in order not to get into a dead end.

4. Verification of the strategy of interaction in the team and work with personnel. The situation in the country can bring some surprises and not very good news every day. People are all different and the reaction to any events may differ. Take into account what is happening at the moment and try to quickly adapt your requests to the specific moment.

In addition, to maintain business sustainability, it is important for the HR function to provide employees and managers with the necessary technical capabilities and knowledge to competently manage teams in the current circumstances and virtual work of teams remotely. Many organizations were not ready to quickly change the operational model of personnel management and adapt to new unplanned realities. Therefore, we have identified 5 basic areas of joint work of HR teams and business in dealing with the consequences of the main threats due to the pandemic (Vitkovska, 2022) and during the war:

1. Assessment of the impact of threats on personnel management (organization of operational monitoring of the state of health of employees; creation of conditions for limiting the movement of employees by ensuring remote work; ensuring timeliness of information transfer to employees; ensuring the desire of employees to work effectively in conditions of potential danger).

2. Movement of workers (creation of means of control over the location of workers outside the boundaries of work; control over the passing of tests of workers, regarding the safety of working conditions and the state of health).

3. Protection of workers (providing workers with individual safety equipment for full-time and freelance workers; assessment of the quality of pay for workers who are in self-isolation, temporarily occupied territories or on sick leave; support for workers during the closure of preschool or general educational institutions, access to bomb shelters).

4. Organization of work (technical support of employees with remote work, monitoring of the productivity of such work; creation of means of cyber protection of data during remote work, intra-organizational notification of missile danger).

5. Ensuring the continuity of business processes (automation of most business processes; formation of optimal personnel; stabilization of processes associated with interruptions in the supply of raw materials, information or communications).

Conclusions / Висновки

So, today it is impossible to manage a staff/team/employee in a normal mode, the main focus in management has been shifted to the “human”. Today’s technologies, psychological trainings, state support, creativity of management and HR managers all contribute to faster adaptation of “human” management in conditions of constant threats. The expansion and complexity of the roles and functions of HR managers taking into account the new requirements of conducting business today, shifting the emphasis to the quality of their education, forming new abilities and skills necessary for carrying out new activities in conditions of constant threats is a trend in the preparation of a high-quality composition of the HR team of any which company.

References

- Peniuk, V. O. (2020). Osoblyvosti HR-menedzhmentu v umovakh pandemii [Peculiarities of HR management in pandemic conditions]. *Visnyk Chernivetskoho torhovelno-ekonomichnoho instytutu. Ekonomichni nauky – Bulletin of the Chernivtsi Trade and Economic Institute. Economic sciences*, 4(80), 138–151. <http://doi.org/10.34025/2310-8185-2020-4.80.10> (in Ukrainian)
- Vitkovska, O. (2022). *HR menedzhment pid chas viiny: yak pikluyatysia pro personal* [HR management during the war: how to take care of personnel]. <https://hurma.work/blog/hr-menedzhment-pid-chas-viiny-yak-pikluyatysya-pro-personal/> (in Ukrainian)